

On the Product of the Square-free Divisor of a Natural Number

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Abstract In this paper we study the product of the square-free divisor of a natural number $P_{sd}(n) = \prod_{\substack{d|n \\ \mu(d) \neq 0}} d$. According to the Dirichlet divisor problem, we turn to study the asymptotic formula of $\sum_{n \leq x} \log P_{sd}(n)$. This article uses the hyperbolic summation and the convolution method to obtain a better error term.

Keywords Square-free number, Dirichlet divisor problem, hyperbolic summation, convolution.

§1. Introduction and main results

F.Smarandache introduced the function $P_d(n) := \prod_{d|n} d$ in Problem 25^[1]. Now we define a similar function $P_{sd}(n)$, which denotes the product of all square-free divisors of n , i.e.,

$$P_{sd}(n) := \prod_{\substack{d|n \\ \mu(d) \neq 0}} d.$$

In the present paper, we shall prove the following Theorem.

Theorem. We have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \log P_{sd}(n) = A_1 x \log^2 x + A_2 x \log x + A_3 x + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(-D(\log x)^{\frac{3}{5}}) (\log \log x)^{-\frac{1}{5}}),$$

where A_1, A_2, A_3 are constants, $D > 0$ is an absolute constant.

Notations. $[x] = \max_{k \in \mathbb{Z}} \{k \leq x\}$, $\psi(t) = t - [t] - \frac{1}{2}$, $\psi_1(t) = \int_0^t \psi(u) du$. $\mu(n)$ is the *Mobius* function. ε denotes a fixed small positive constant which may be different at each occurrence. γ is the Euler constant. $B_1, B_2, B_3, C_1, C_2, D_1, D_2, D_3, D_4$ are constants.

§2. Some preliminary lemmas

We need the following results:

Lemma 1. Let $f(n)$ be an arithmetical function for which

$$\sum_{n \leq x} f(n) = \sum_{j=1}^l x^{a_j} P_j(\log x) + O(x^a),$$

$$\sum_{n \leq x} |f(n)| = O(x^{a_1} \log^r x),$$

where $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_l > \frac{1}{k} > a \geq 0$, $r \geq 0$, $P_1(t), \dots, P_l(t)$ are polynomials in t of degrees not exceeding r , and $k \geq 1$ is a fixed integer. If

$$h(n) = \sum_{d^k | n} \mu_i(d) f(n/d^k), \quad i \geq 1$$

then

$$\sum_{n \leq x} h(n) = \sum_{j=1}^l x^{a_j} R_j(\log x) + \delta(x),$$

where $R_1(t), \dots, R_l(t)$ are polynomials in t of degrees not exceeding r . and for some $D > 0$

$$\delta(x) \ll x^{\frac{1}{k}} \exp(-D(\log x)^{\frac{3}{5}} (\log \log x)^{-\frac{1}{5}}).$$

Proof. See Theorem 14.2 of A. Ivic^[3] when $l = 1$ and the similar proof is used when $l > 1$.

Lemma 2. Suppose that $f(u) \in C^3[u_1, u_2]$, then

$$\sum_{u_1 < n \leq u_2} f(n) = \int_{u_1}^{u_2} f(u) du - \psi(u) f(u) \Big|_{u_1}^{u_2} + \psi_1(u) f'(u) \Big|_{u_1}^{u_2} - \int_{u_1}^{u_2} \psi_1(u) f''(u) du.$$

Lemma 3. We have

$$\sum_{1 \leq m \leq y} \frac{1}{m} = \log y + \gamma - \frac{\psi(y)}{y} + O\left(\frac{1}{y^2}\right), \quad y \geq 1.$$

Lemma 4. We have

$$\sum_{1 \leq m \leq y} \log m = y \log y - y - \psi(y) \log y + \frac{\psi_1(y)}{y} + D_1 + O\left(\frac{1}{y^2}\right), \quad y \geq 1.$$

Lemma 5. We have

$$\sum_{1 \leq m \leq y} \frac{\log m}{m^2} = -\frac{\log y}{y} - \frac{1}{y} + D_3 + O\left(\frac{\log y}{y^2}\right), \quad y \geq 1.$$

Lemma 6. We have

$$\sum_{1 \leq m \leq y} \frac{\log^2 m}{m^2} = -\frac{\log^2 y}{y} - \frac{2 \log y}{y} - \frac{2}{y} + D_4 + O\left(\frac{\log^2 y}{y^2}\right), \quad y \geq 1.$$

Lemma 7. We have

$$\sum_{n \leq y} d(n) = y \log y + (2\gamma - 1)y + O(y^{\frac{1}{3}}).$$

Lemma 8. We have

$$\sum_{n \leq y} d(n) n^{-\frac{1}{2}} = 2y^{\frac{1}{2}} \log y + (4\gamma - 4)y^{\frac{1}{2}} - 2\gamma + 3 + O(y^{-\frac{1}{6}}).$$

Lemma 9. We have

$$\sum_{n \leq y} d(n)n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \log n = 2y^{\frac{1}{2}} \log^2 y + (4\gamma - 8)y^{\frac{1}{2}} \log y + (16 - 8\gamma)y^{\frac{1}{2}} + 8\gamma - 16 + O(y^{-\frac{1}{6}} \log y).$$

Lemma 2 is the Euler-Maclaurin summation formula (see [2]). Lemma 3, 4, 5, 6 follow from Lemma 2 directly. Lemma 7 is a classical result about the Dirichlet divisor problem. Lemma 8, 9 can be easily obtained by Lemma 2 and Lemma 7.

§3. Proof of the theorem

It is easily seen that

$$\log P_{sd}(n) = \sum_{n=dl, \mu(d) \neq 0} \log d,$$

which implies that ($\sigma > 1$)

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\log P_{sd}(n)}{n^s} &= \zeta(s) \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} \frac{|\mu(d)| \log d}{d^s} = \zeta(s) \left(- \sum_{d=1}^{\infty} \frac{|\mu(d)|}{d^s} \right)' \\ &= -\zeta(s) \left(\frac{\zeta(s)}{\zeta(2s)} \right)' = -\zeta(s)\zeta'(s) \frac{1}{\zeta(2s)} + 2\zeta^2(s)\zeta'(2s) \frac{1}{\zeta^2(2s)} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} h_1(n)n^{-s} + 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} h_2(n)n^{-s}. \end{aligned}$$

where

$$h_1(n) = \sum_{d^2|n} \mu(d)f_1(n/d^2), \quad f_1(n) = \sum_{m|n} \log m;$$

$$h_2(n) = \sum_{d^2|n} \mu_2(d)f_2(n/d^2), \quad f_2(n) = \sum_{n=m^2k} d(k) \log m, \quad \mu_2(d) = \sum_{n=dk} \mu(d)\mu(k).$$

Our Theorem follows from the following Proposition 1 and Proposition 2.

Proposition 1. We have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} h_1(n) = B_1x \log^2 x + B_2x \log x + B_3x + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(-D(\log x)^{\frac{3}{5}} (\log \log x)^{-\frac{1}{5}})).$$

Proposition 2. We have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} h_2(n) = C_1x \log x + C_2x + O(x^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp(-D(\log x)^{\frac{3}{5}} (\log \log x)^{-\frac{1}{5}})).$$

We only proof Proposition 2. The proof of Proposition 1 is similar and easier. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \leq x} f_2(n) &= \sum_{n \leq x} \sum_{m^2k=n} d(k) \log m = \sum_{m^2n \leq x} d(n) \log m \\ &= \sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \log m \sum_{n \leq \frac{x}{m^2}} d(n) + \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) \sum_{m \leq (\frac{x}{n})^{\frac{1}{2}}} \log m - \sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \log m \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) \\ &= S_1 + S_2 - S_3 \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 7, 5, 6

$$\begin{aligned}
S_1 &= \sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \left(\frac{x}{m^2} \log \frac{x}{m^2} + (2\gamma - 1) \frac{x}{m^2} + O\left(\left(\frac{x}{m^2}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}}\right) \right) \log m \\
&= (x \log x + (2\gamma - 1)x) \sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \frac{\log m}{m^2} - 2x \sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \frac{\log^2 m}{m^2} + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{3}} \sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} \frac{\log m}{m^{\frac{2}{3}}}\right) \\
&= (x \log x + (2\gamma - 1)x) \left(-\frac{1}{3} x^{-\frac{1}{3}} \log x - x^{-\frac{1}{3}} + D_3 + O\left(x^{-\frac{2}{3}} \log x\right) \right) \\
&\quad - 2x \left(-\frac{1}{9} x^{-\frac{1}{3}} \log^2 x - \frac{2}{3} x^{-\frac{1}{3}} \log x - 2x^{-\frac{1}{3}} + D_4 + O\left(x^{-\frac{2}{3}} \log x\right) \right) + O\left(x^{\frac{4}{9} + \varepsilon}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 4, 8, 9

$$\begin{aligned}
S_2 &= \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x}{n}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \log \frac{x}{n} - \left(\frac{x}{n}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + D_1 + O\left(\log \frac{x}{n}\right) \right) \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2} x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x - x^{\frac{1}{2}}\right) \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) n^{-\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{1}{2} x^{\frac{1}{2}} \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) \log n n^{-\frac{1}{2}} \\
&\quad + D_1 \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) + O\left(\log x \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n)\right) \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{2} x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x - x^{\frac{1}{2}}\right) \left(\frac{2}{3} x^{\frac{1}{6}} \log x + (4\gamma - 4)x^{\frac{1}{6}} - 2\gamma + 3 + O\left(x^{-\frac{1}{18}}\right)\right) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} x^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{2}{9} x^{\frac{1}{6}} \log^2 x + \frac{1}{3} (4\gamma - 8)x^{\frac{1}{6}} \log x + (16 - 8\gamma)x^{\frac{1}{6}} + 8\gamma - 16 + O\left(x^{-\frac{1}{18}} \log x\right)\right) \\
&\quad + D_1 \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{3} + \varepsilon}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 4 and Lemma 7,

$$\begin{aligned}
S_3 &= \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) \left(\frac{1}{3} x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x - x^{\frac{1}{3}} + D_1 + O(\log x) \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{3} x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) - x^{\frac{1}{3}} \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) + D_1 \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n) \\
&\quad + O\left(\log x \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n)\right) \\
&= \left(\frac{1}{3} x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x - x^{\frac{1}{3}}\right) \left(\frac{1}{3} x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log x + (2\gamma - 1)x^{\frac{1}{3}} + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{9}}\right)\right) \\
&\quad + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{3} + \varepsilon}\right) + D_1 \sum_{n \leq x^{\frac{1}{3}}} d(n)
\end{aligned}$$

Combining the above estimates we get

$$\sum_{n \leq x} f_2(n) = D_3 x \log x + ((2\gamma - 1)D_3 - 2D_4)x + \frac{3 - 2\gamma}{2} x^{\frac{1}{2}} \log x + (5 - 2\gamma)x^{\frac{1}{2}} + O\left(x^{\frac{4}{5} + \varepsilon}\right),$$

which gives Proposition 2 immediately by using Lemma 1 .

References

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